

AN EXPRESSION OF BABUR'S SPIRIT IN XX CENTURY WORLD LITERATURE

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Abstract: This article examines the expression of Babur's spirit in Uzbek and English-speaking Western literature of the 20th century. The images of Babur as a father, child, head of the family, as well as a ruler in the interpretation of English, Indian and Uzbek writers are widely compared. Here, conclusions are drawn based on various excerpts taken from literary works.

Keywords: Zahiriddin Muhammada Babur, Amir Temur, Flora Annie Steel, Muni Lal, Stephan Meredith Edwardes, Khayriddin Sultanov, Pirimkul Kadyrov, Umarshaikh Mirza, Kutlug Nigar Khanum, Humayun Mirza.

INTRODUCTION

It is known that works about Babur form a unique artistic system in world and Uzbek literature. In particular, the short stories and novels of Flora Annie Steel, Stephan Meredith Edwardes, Muni Lal in English and Indian prose, P. Kadirov, Kh. Sultanov in Uzbek prose confirm our opinions. In these works, the human form and spiritual world of the king and poet Babur are given in a wide scope. In this regard, we will try to compare the proportional and different aspects of the works mentioned above from the point of view of the depiction of mental states.

MAIN PART

While studying the pages about Babur's life, the English writer F.A. Steel found that the scene related to the death of Babur's father Umarshaikh Mirza, expressed in historical sources and "Baburnama", was reflected in almost all works about the historical figure. In F.A. Steel's novel we read: "A messenger stood before him; one who had come far and fast. And in his hand was a blue kerchief; therefore he was a messenger of death. A sudden surge of resentful life-blood seemed to stop the boyish heart with its tumultuous claim for free passage. A sudden spasm of remorse for idle thoughts sent the son's memory back to his father's kindness"¹.

In fact, when Babur was 12 years old, he heard about his father's tragic death. It should be noted that the English writer was well aware of aspects specific to the Eastern mentality. The above passage seems to have been written by an Uzbek writer. This is confirmed by the blue kerchief in the hand of the

¹ Steel A. King-Errant.-New York: Frederick A.Stokes Company, 1912. – P.5-6.

messenger who came to Babur. Because in the East, a blue kerchief represents death. Of course, this was an unexpected event for Babur, who was busy with childhood feelings and entertainment. The writer impressively reveals his mental state in these sad moments. Images and metaphors such as "the young man's heart stopped beating", "frightened doves flapping their white wings", "the frightened soul also flew away" represent the changes in Babur's mentality. Most importantly, Babur's remembrance of his father's kindness in such moments also has an oriental meaning.

These mental states are reflected in the novel "Starry Nights" as follows: "Babur, who was just now surrounded by elegant feelings like a flower, felt that the news of death was a snake that came out of this flower. The terrible news made Babur silent... Babur felt with his whole body that he would no longer see his father for life, and a bitter sense of separation suddenly filled his being, and tears fell from his eyes. Consequently, the depiction of Babur's troubled moments by English and Uzbek writers is very harmonious. If F.A. Steel enriched it with oriental content, P.Kadirov also relies on historical facts.

Babur tried to learn from Amir Timur in his life. This is expressed as follows in the work of M. Lal: "Babar was obsessed throughout his career with the feeling that God had chosen him to recover for his dynasty the glory that once engulfed Timur. That is why a major setback did not cause him to despair. On the other hand, with failures he could generate more energy from within him, and continue to march forward in an endeavor to keep what he believed was his pledge with destiny."² In fact, Babur, who considered himself the true successor of Amir Temur, tried to be stable at all times. Because he believed that he was chosen to be the king not by chance, but to save the state founded by Timur. Kh. Sultanov's images are also in line with this: "While wandering around the places where the footsteps of his flamboyant ancestor Temurbek were touched or where his immortal legacy spread, he always communicates absently with the owners, seeks comfort from his lessons, records every historical information related to him with special respect in the notebook of the heart. While evaluating the political and moral behavior of the statesmen of his time or those who passed before or after him, His Holiness Babur always takes the activity of Amir Temur as the main criterion. The above picture also confirms that Babur looked at his grandfather Sahibkiran with great devotion. Even when he was in trouble, he sought solace from Amir Temur's teachings. Babur's communication with Sahibqiran in absentia, seeking comfort from his teachings, writing down

² Muni Lal. Babar: life and times. – New Delhi: Vikas Publishing House PVT LTD, 1977. – P. 30.

historical information related to him in his heart notebook, and considering his work as a standard for himself can be seen.

The English writer Anna Steel very impressively describes the death of Mrs. Kutlug Nigar Khanum and the pains that took place in Babur's heart during this process: "There was no longer any doubt that the Khanum had contracted measles in its worst repressed form. He bent over her to give the last caress before Death claimed the body and it lay soulless, impure. But she? She was received into the Mercy of God. On the Sunday morning, he put his strong shoulder under the light bier and carried it to the Garden of the New Year. Babar, holding the head and Kasim, his foster brother, the feet, laid the light, muslin-swathed, tinsel-bound corpse in the long, low niche, cut coffin-wise in the side. His voice scarcely trembled at all as he laid a handful of earth upon the breast with the solemn words of admonition and hope. Out of the dust I made you, and to dust I return you, to raise you yet once more out of the dust upon the Day of Resurrection"³. Babur feels guilty for his mother's illness. Babur's image as a good son is embodied in images such as him standing on his mother's head holding his mother's warm palm. The events such as his sadness during the burial process of his mother, tears filling his eyes, throwing flowers on her with his own hands, and squatting in front of the grave are sad and painful for the king-poet. It should be emphasized that the English writer effectively expressed this life reality in an oriental spirit.

CONCLUSION

Babur tried to learn from his grandfather Amir Temur in life. Muni Lal has convincingly expressed these processes. Khairiddin Sultanov, as an artist of the soul, impressively reflected the warm and pleasant moments and painful experiences of Babur's heart and soul. This is especially evident in the images of his absent communication with Sahibqiran, seeking comfort from his teachings, writing historical facts related to him in his notebook, and measuring his work as a standard for himself.

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³ Steel A. King-Errant. –New York: Frederick A.Stokes Company, 1912. – P.83-84.

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